

Student Voice: A Staff Guide

for those responsible for responding to student voice

You may wish to read this Guide in conjunction with:

- The Student Voice Timeline – staff planner (this explains what happens ‘behind the scenes’ of Student Voice Meetings);
 - The Student Voice Timeline for Students (this sets out the Student Voice events for the year); and
 - Student Voice: The Student Guide (this aims to set student expectations of Student Voice Meeting and Module Evaluation feedback processes within the department).
-

1. The importance of effective student voice mechanisms

Student trust is crucial to an effective student voice system¹. It is well established that closing the loop on student feedback enhances trust in the system, increasing the likelihood of students participating in future surveys² and linking to an increase in student satisfaction³, with ineffective student voice systems reportedly causing student demotivation⁴, scepticism⁵ and resentment of student voice mechanisms⁶.

For staff, effective student voice mechanisms promote open discussion between students and staff⁷, encourage staff development opportunities⁸ and, importantly, increase the reliability of the student feedback data collected⁹. Engaging with student voice to enhance our teaching can assist with those seeking professional recognition via Advance HE’s Fellowship route: the Professional Standards Framework¹⁰ places overt emphasis on the effectiveness and impact of teaching; the context in which the teaching takes place; and how more inclusive approaches ensure all learners feel respected, valued and have equity in opportunity to succeed.

There are many ways in which student input on their experiences can be garnered and many of you will work with students as partners in your teaching and learning practice. This guide concentrates on just the ‘traditional’ feedback models of Student Voice Meetings and Module Evaluation Questionnaires. A flowchart overview of each of these processes is shown at [Appendix 1](#).

An overview of how these processes fit with support provided for staff at departmental level is shown at [Appendix 2](#).

¹ Young, H. and Jerome, L. (2020), *Student voice in higher education: Opening the loop*. British Educational Research Journal, 46: 688-705. <https://doi.org/10.1002/berj.3603>

² See, for example, Watson, S. (2003). *Closing the feedback loop: Ensuring effective action from student feedback*. Tertiary Education and Management 9: 145-147; Williams, R. and Brennan, J. (2003). *Collecting and using student feedback on quality and standards of learning and teaching in Higher Education*. Bristol: Higher Education Funding Council for England; Buckley, A (2012) *Making it Count: Reflecting on the National Student Survey in the process of enhancement*. York: Higher Education Academy.

³ Williams, R. and Brennan, J. (2003), n1 above

⁴ Caulfield, J (2007) *What Motivates Students to Provide Feedback to Teachers About Teaching and Learning? An Expectancy Theory Perspective*. International Journal for the Scholarship of Teaching & Learning, 1(1), 1-20

⁵ Leckey, J and Neill, N. (2001). *Quantifying Quality: The importance of student feedback*. Quality in Higher Education, 7(1), 19-32

⁶ Buckley, A. (2012), n1 above

⁷ Cook-Sather, A. (2009). *From traditional accountability to shared responsibility: The benefits and challenges of student consultants gathering midcourse feedback in college classrooms*. Assessment & Evaluation in Higher Education, 34(2), 231-241.

⁸ Blair, E., & Valdez Noel, K. (2014). *Improving higher education practice through student evaluation systems: is the student voice being heard?*. Assessment & Evaluation in Higher Education, 39(7), 879-894.

⁹ Buckley, A. (2012), n1 above

¹⁰ Advance HE (2023), *Professional Standards Framework (PSF 2023)*, available from <https://www.advance-he.ac.uk/teaching-and-learning/psf> (accessed 2 February 2024)

2. Aims of the feedback cycle

The four aims of our student voice feedback cycle are as follows:

- 1 Ensure student **expectations** are realistically set, both in terms of what they are feeding back on, and what 'responding to students' means
- 2 Ensure staff feel **supported** to close the loop on feedback provided by students
- 3 Encourage a **higher response rate** to Termly Review, Module Evaluation and Student Voice Meeting input, to ensure we are responding to views representative of the cohort
- 4 Ensure all students (as far as possible) are **aware of the actions** following Termly Review, MEQ and SVM processes in a consistent manner

3. Achieving the Aims

- 1 Ensure student **expectations** are realistically set, both in terms of what they are feeding back on, and what 'responding to students' means

To achieve Aim 1, 'Student Voice: The Student Guide' is made available to all students, setting out what appropriate feedback consists of and making clear to students that 'responding to student needs' does not necessarily mean 'doing what students want'. The Guide sets out clearly that popularity is not to be confused with good teaching, and that several of our practices are underpinned by sound reasoning. However, the Guide does make clear that we will always listen to what students have to say, so concerns regarding, e.g. group work, cannot be dismissed without a response.

- 2 Ensure staff feel **supported** to close the loop on feedback provided by students

To achieve Aim 2, four elements will come together:

1. For modules with teaching teams, modular responses to Termly Review and MEQ will be drafted following a module team meeting or other correspondence within the team, to ensure all team members can contribute. The burden is not solely on the module leader,

and responsibility for collating the modular response can be shared by module team members;

2. Departmental team meetings, so far as possible, will be scheduled before the date for responding to the Termly Review (see [Appendix 2](#)). During these meetings, we will discuss themes across modules, validity of response rates, as well as responses to module feedback. The aim of discussions in departmental meetings is to understand how colleagues are responding to feedback and to identify whether there are themes across modules that can be picked up via a departmental approach/response;
3. At the annual departmental away day, time will be put aside to discuss Termly Review/MEQ themes from the year, and the SVM action plan. We will discuss lessons learnt over the year and any suggestions for improvement in the following year;
4. If a module team member or module leader has a concern about comments raised by students during the Student Voice process or is unsure how to respond to a modular particular issue, they can contact the Programme Leader for guidance. If any member of staff has any concerns about the administration of the Student Voice process, they can contact the Head of Department for advice.

3

Encourage a **higher response rate** to Termly Review, Module Evaluation and Student Voice Meeting input, to ensure we are responding to views representative of the cohort

To achieve Aim 3, we will be mindful of evidence which shows that response rates increase where (a) surveys are conducted 'on the organisation's time'; and (b) the feedback loop is closed effectively.

In all cases:

- Feedback will be gathered at the start of a taught session;
- Responses will be provided orally and in writing at the start of a taught session; and
- Where no change is possible, the reasons for this will always be explained.

In particular:

1. Termly Review: Module teams will collate responses via mobile device at the start of a module session and respond to feedback at the start of a live session within two teaching weeks of collecting responses;
2. SVM: Those delivering live sessions in the relevant week will set aside five minutes at the start of the session to:
 - a. allow all students to complete the SVM survey via mobile device; and
 - b. following the SVM, permit a representative from the SVM to share the SVM Rolling Action Plan either live during the session or by way of a recording played at the start of the session.

3. MEQ: Module teams will collate responses via mobile device at the start of a module session and changes made will be brought to the attention of current and future cohorts by way of saving the responses on the VLE in a central 'Responses to MEQ feedback' document, and by way of a note in the next cohort's module handbook explaining how changes have been made in response to the feedback of the previous year's students.

The tone of responses will also be important: we can, and at times will, say 'no' to students. We need to be sure that the wording used does not give the impression of 'batting away' perceived concerns.

4

Ensure all students (as far as possible) are **aware of the actions** following Termly Review, MEQ and SVM processes in a consistent manner

To achieve Aim 4, the overarching concern is to respond to feedback uniformly to ensure the student voice process is not undermined.

In particular:

1. Termly Review: all module teams will respond to Termly Review input in class time by way of a written response shown and discussed at the start of a module session and saved on the VLE;
2. MEQ: all module teams will respond to themes arising from MEQs in writing, saved in module handbooks for the following cohort and saved centrally on the VLE/Teams so students who have provided the MEQ feedback can see how this has been used;
3. SVM: as a departmental team, we will respond to every student comment made in the SVM survey, provide a copy of this to all students and share the Rolling Action Plan with all students at the start of a live session.

Student Voice Meetings: Overview

Student voice meetings are held three times per year. For each meeting, the process below is followed:

Module Evaluation: Overview

Termly Review (mid-term)

Module Evaluation Questionnaire (end of module)

Overview of departmental support for staff involved in Module Evaluation and Student Voice Meetings

